

Emerging Green Consumerism in India: A Study of Knowledge, Awareness and Attitude of FMCG Consumers

Chandrashekhar C

Research Scholar, Karnataka

ABSTRACT

Green lifestyle and ethical consumption have become increasingly popular strategies in moving towards eco-friendly society and combating universal scarcity. Many businesses and industries are joining for this green movement, either out of real interest in saving the planet or a desire to capitalize the growing consumer demand for green products. Environmentalism plays crucial role in attracting potential consumers. This created new business opportunities. Many firms are slowly adapting green practices in manufacturing and marketing activities as a part of social responsibility. However a large number of research have been conducted in developed countries on green consumerism, but in India it is still in the infancy stage and lacks behind in the field of studying green consumer behavior. The new green movement needs to reach everyone, that will take much more time and effort. The government, the organization and the consumers have to work collectively for bringing the ecological balance.

Keywords: Green products, FMCG Products, Eco-friendly products, Consumer perception, Environmental Consciousness, Consumer awareness, Consumer Attitude.

INTRODUCTION

World over, economic growth has come at the cost of environment only. Over the last few decades increase in global warming, air pollution, poor management of waste, growing water scarcity, falling in ground water level, water pollution, deforestation, loss of biodiversity, soil degradation, acid rains, depletion of the ozone layer from chlorofluorocarbons and many more critical environmental issues made the environmentalism has very important issue. As a result, there is an increase in interest of customers towards environmental protection and sustainable development. The customers are decided to use those goods which are safe for environment and good for health.

Green consumers are those consumers who buy eco-friendly products with the concern about environmental issues and who searches for evidence in label to recognize environmental friendly product.

Attitude refers to a mental state that consist of feelings, emotions or opinions evolved in response to an external situation. An attitude can be momentary or can develop into a habitual position that has long-term influence on a consumer attempts to evaluate a product, services or the like he or she will develop an attitude about the thing being evaluated.

FMCG (Fast Moving Consumer Goods) are the products that are sold quickly at relatively low cost. Though the absolute profit made on FMCG products is relatively small, they generally sell in large quantities, so the cumulative profit on such products can be large. Examples of FMCG generally includes a wide range of frequently purchased consumer products such as toiletries, soap, cosmetics, mouth freshening products etc.

According to the American Marketing Association (AMA) "Green Marketing is the marketing of products that are presumed to be environmentally safe. It incorporates a broad range of activities, including product modification, changes to the production process, packaging changes, as well as modifying advertising".

Polonsky "Green marketing consists of all activities designed to generate and facilitate any exchanges intended to satisfy human needs or wants, such that satisfaction of those needs and wants occurs, with minimal detrimental impact on the natural environment".

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

The concept of marketing of green products started in 1960s, formalised and generalised the late 1980s and early 1990s, green marketing was defined as the study of positive and negative aspects of pollution and depletion of energy sources (Akehurst et al., 2012). As per another definition, green marketing consists of all planned activities to generate and facilitate exchanges in order to satisfy human needs and desires with the least possible impact on the environment (Polonsky, 1994). Peattie and Charter (2003) defined green marketing as the holistic management process responsible for identifying, anticipating and satisfying customer needs in a profitable and sustainable manner. This definition emphasizes the holistic approach towards green marketing. It means green marketing involves green strategies from new product development to modifications in the marketing mix and from packaging to advertising. Peattie (2001) stated that green marketing has evolved through three stages. First stage emerged since 1980s when green marketing was newly initiated in the industry. The second stage occurred in 1990s when marketers experienced backlash for green marketing. Marketers apprehended that consumers' concern for environment and green products did not translate into purchasing behavior. The third stage began since the year 2000. During this phase, green marketing got a new momentum with the implementation of more advanced technology, stricter regulations by governments and enhancement of global environmental awareness level. Based on these three stages, the research preferences of the researchers changed from time to time. From the 1970s the researchers began to develop marketing with an environmental perspective. A majority of those early works centered on the study of the relations between environmental concern and behavior (consumers' participation in recycling systems) and on the characterization of the green consumer (Chamorro et al., 2009). Research on green marketing had mirrored the various waves of social concern about the environment. Up till the early nineties, the research on green marketing remained largely descriptive and lacked academic perspective and rigor (Jain & Kaur, 2004). During this period, research had a 'managerial perspective' focusing primarily on issues of 'green consumer behaviour', advertising and market segmentation. From the mid-1990s onwards, a new research agenda emerged which focused on broader and more conceptual issues regarding the physical sustainability of marketing (Peattie, 1999). In this new period, researchers focused on a range of issues wider than those considered previously (Chamorro et al, 2009). Since nineties, the researchers have started academically analysing consumers' green attitudes and behaviour, thus providing managerial insights to green marketers to market their green ideas and products more effectively. Chamorro et al (2009) reviewed the main characteristics of research papers on green marketing during the period 1993-2003. The study concluded that a total of around 26 percent of the research papers under analysis were theoretical in content, while around 74 percent were empirical studies; the most commonly used data collection technique was the survey; a majority of the empirical studies were based on national level or lower; the empirical studies were made use of diverse statistical techniques with regression analysis and structural equation models.

Need for the study

This study tries to investigate the consumer awareness and attitude towards eco-friendly FMCG products. People of Mysuru are relatively conscious about sustainable development, so need to examine their attitude towards Green products and to explore the barriers for purchasing eco-friendly products.

Objectives

1. To study the conceptual framework of Green Consumerism.
2. To assess the level of knowledge and concern of consumers towards Green products.
3. To examine the awareness and attitude of consumers towards eco-friendly products.
4. To explore the barriers to purchase the eco-friendly FMCG products.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research has selected the respondents by using convenience sampling method with a sample size of 100 from Mysore city in Karnataka. Primary data have been extracted by using structured questionnaire. SPSS software have been used to analyze the data. Frequency and ANOVA tests are used for analysis. Tables are used for interpretation.

Analysis and Interpretation

The results of the analysis of the collected data are presented below:

Table 1: Demographic profile of respondents

Demographic variables	Classification	No. of respondents	Percentage
Gender	Male	69	69%
	Female	31	31%
Marital Status	Married	84	84%
	Single	16	16%
Age	Below 20	02	02%
	21-30	17	17%
	31-40	44	44%
	41-50	25	25%
	Above 51	12	12%
Education	Higher secondary	01	01%
	Under Graduation	12	12%
	Graduates	63	63%
	Post graduates	15	15%
	Professionals	09	09%
Status	Employees	40	40%
	Businessman	13	13%
	Professionals	24	24%
	Homemaker	13	13%
	Retired persons	07	07%
	Others	03	03%
Monthly income	Below 25000	27	27%
	25001-50000	50	50%
	50001-75000	14	14%
	75001-100000	04	04%
	Above 100001	05	05%

Source: Field survey

- A study of the above table and revealed that majority of the respondents of the study (69%) was male and 31% of them are female. A vast majority of them (84%) were married and the remaining 16% of them were single.
- The table revealed that 44% of the respondents belonging to the age group 31-40, 25% of them are in the age group of 41-50, 17% of them are in the age group of 21-30, 12% are above the age of 51 and 2% percentage of the respondents are below 20.
- On the basis of education 63% of the respondents are found to be graduates, 15% of them are post graduates, 12% of them are under graduates, 09% of the respondents are professionals and 01% of them are having the education of higher secondary.
- On the basis of employment status of the respondents 40% of them are employees, 24% of them were professional, 13% of them homemaker, 13% of them were businessman, 7% of them retired persons and 3% of them belong to other category.
- A majority of the respondents (50%) are having the monthly family income of Rs. 25001-50000, 27% of them are below the income Rs. 25000, 14% of them are having the income of Rs. 50001-75000, 4% of them are above income of Rs.100001, 5% of them are having the monthly family income from Rs.75001-100000.
- A majority of the respondents (49%) are having the family size of 4 members, 38% of them are having the family size 3 & below, 13% of the respondents are having family size of 5 and above.

Table: 2 Sources of Information

Sl. NO	Source of Information	Percentage
1.	Radio	11
2.	Television	08
3.	News paper	12
4.	Outdoor	18

	advertisements	
5.	Product label	31
6.	Websites	05
7.	Word of mouth	15

Source: Field survey

The study reveals that nearly 31% of the respondents believe that product label is major sources of awareness towards eco-friendly FMCG products. 18% of the respondents said that outdoor advertisements have made them to aware of eco-friendly products. 15% of them found that word of mouth is sources of information and 11% & 12% find that newspaper and radio has made them aware of green products. 8% and 5% of them found that television and newspaper has made them to know about eco-friendly FMCG products. It is found that television and websites are weak in spreading awareness about eco- friendly products.

Table 3 Stimulus to buy Eco-Friendly FMCG Products

Sl. No	Stimuli	Percentage
1	For serving environment	33%
2	For health factors	46%
3	For the appreciation from others	14%
4	For pressure from someone	05%
5	For I saw many people purchase them	12%

Source: Field survey

The table reveals that majority (46%) of the respondents buy eco-friendly products for health reasons.33% of them purchasing eco-friendly products for serving the environment. 14% of them purchasing them for the appreciation from others. 12% of them purchase it for that they saw many people purchase them and 5% of them are buying it for pressure from someone.

Testing of Hypotheses

1. To assess the level of consumers knowledge towards Green products

HO: There is no significant difference in environmental knowledge and concern of the respondents among respondents with different status.

H1: There is a significant difference in environmental knowledge and concern of the respondents among respondents with different status.

Table 4

ANOVA							
			Sum of Squares	DF	Mean Square	F	Sig.
ENVIRNEMNTAL KNOWLEDGE/AW ARENES * STATUS	Between Groups	(Combined)	116.281	5	23.256	3.217	.007
	Within Groups		4626.575	640	7.229		
	Total		4742.856	645			

Source: Field survey.

Statistical inference: The result obtained through ANOVA in table 4 shows the status of respondents are having significant difference in level of environmental knowledge at 5% significance level. The calculated value is more than the 0.05 value. Hence null hypothesis is rejected and the alternative hypothesis is accepted.

2. To assess the level of consumers environmental concern towards Green products

HO: There is no significant difference in environmental concern of the respondents among respondents with different status.

H1: There is a significant difference in environmental concern of the respondents among the different status of respondents.

Table 5

ANOVA							
ENVIRNEMNTAL COMMITMENT * STATUS	Between Groups	(Combined)	1466.010	5	293.202	10.303	.000
	Within Groups		18213.067	640	28.458		
	Total		19679.077	645			

Source: Field survey

Statistical inference: The result obtained through ANOVA in table 5 gives the status of respondents are having no significant difference towards environmental concern at 5% significance level. The calculated value is less than the 0.05 value. Hence, null hypothesis is accepted.

3. Relationship between consumer awareness and education of respondents

HO: There is no significant difference between consumer awareness and education of the respondents.

H1: There is a significant difference between consumer awareness and education of the respondents.

Table 6

ANOVA						
		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
I am aware of eco-friendly products and its relative merits	Between Groups	.445	3	.148	.572	.636
	Within Groups	11.677	45	.259		
	Total	12.122	48			
I am aware of the harm that non- biodegradable goods can cause to the earth.	Between Groups	.927	3	.309	.910	.444
	Within Groups	15.277	45	.339		
	Total	16.204	48			
I can differentiate between eco- friendly product and harmful products.	Between Groups	.691	3	.230	.916	.441
	Within Groups	11.309	45	.251		
	Total	12.000	48			

Source: Field survey

Statistical inference: The result obtained through ANOVA in table 6 reveals that, at 5% significance level there is a significant difference in consumer awareness and education of the respondents. The calculated value is more than the 0.05 value. Hence, null hypothesis is rejected and alternative hypothesis is accepted.

4. The study of consumers attitude based on their income group.

HO: There is no significant difference between consumers attitude towards eco-friendly products and their income.

H1: There is a significant difference between consumer attitudes towards eco-friendly products and their income.

Table 7

ANOVA						
		Sum of Squares	DF	Mean Square	F	Sig.
I read label before buying to know if contents are environmentally safe	Between Groups	.655	3	.218	1.051	.380
	Within Groups	9.345	45	.208		
	Total	10.000	48			
Eco-friendly products are not widely advertised and hence not popular.	Between Groups	.344	3	.115	.340	.797
	Within Groups	15.207	45	.338		
	Total	15.551	48			
I always look into the products having less hazardous substances in it.	Between Groups	.698	3	.233	.522	.670
	Within Groups	20.077	45	.446		
	Total	20.776	48			
While shopping, I always check if the products I buy are environmentally safe.	Between Groups	.064	3	.021	.055	.983
	Within Groups	17.609	45	.391		
	Total	17.673	48			
I go in search of eco-friendly products if it is not available in oneshop.	Between Groups	.590	3	.197	.591	.624
	Within Groups	14.961	45	.332		
	Total	15.551	48			
I take a chance to convince my family members to buy eco-friendly products	Between Groups	.430	3	.143	.557	.646
	Within Groups	11.570	45	.257		
	Total	12.000	48			
I appreciate the package/design of green products.	Between Groups	.867	3	.289	.779	.512
	Within Groups	16.684	45	.371		
	Total	17.551	48			
I believe the information on eco-friendly product package.	Between Groups	1.442	3	.481	1.533	.219
	Within Groups	14.109	45	.314		
	Total	15.551	48			
I pay attention to eco-friendly advertisements	Between Groups	.205	3	.068	.229	.875
	Within Groups	13.427	45	.298		
	Total	13.633	48			
I believe in the eco-friendly advertisements.	Between Groups	.126	3	.042	.154	.926
	Within Groups	12.282	45	.273		
	Total	12.408	48			
I am ready to pay little extra price for eco-friendly products.	Between Groups	.573	3	.191	.843	.478
	Within Groups	10.202	45	.227		
	Total	10.776	48			
I am ready to adapt green lifestyle.	Between Groups	.541	3	.180	.648	.588
	Within Groups	12.520	45	.278		
	Total	13.061	48			
Eco-friendly products will	Between	.250	3	.083	.212	.888

notperform as same as normal brands.	Groups					
	Within Groups	17.709	45	.394		
	Total	17.959	48			

Source: Field survey

Statistical inference: The result obtained through ANOVA in table 7 reveals that there is a significant difference between consumer attitudes towards eco-friendly products and the income group of respondents. It is seen at 5% significance level. The calculated value is more than the 0.05 value in majority of the cases. Hence null hypothesis is rejected and alternative hypothesis is accepted.

5. To explore the barriers to purchase eco-friendly FMCG products

H0: There is no significant difference in barriers to the purchase of eco-friendly products among the respondents of different income group.

H1: There is a significant difference in barriers to the purchase of eco-friendly products among the respondents of different income group.

Table 8

ANOVA						
		Sum of Squares	DF	Mean Square	F	Sig.
High cost	Between Groups	3.518	5	.704	.912	.473
	Within Groups	493.795	640	.772		
	Total	497.313	645			
Lack of availability	Between Groups	8.092	5	1.618	.741	.593
	Within Groups	1398.764	640	2.186		
	Total	1406.856	645			
Lack of knowledge about eco-friendly products	Between Groups	27.748	5	5.550	6.348	.000
	Within Groups	559.540	640	.874		
	Total	587.288	645			
Unaware of benefits	Between Groups	24.035	5	4.807	4.530	.000
	Within Groups	679.074	640	1.061		
	Total	703.108	645			
Non-durability	Between Groups	5.666	5	1.133	1.502	.187
	Within Groups	482.788	640	.754		
	Total	488.454	645			

Source: Field survey

Statistical Inference:

1. The result obtained through ANOVA in table 8 explains that lack of knowledge about the green products and unaware of the benefit are having the value of less than 0.05 so there is no significant difference between in the above barriers and income group of the respondent. It means lack of knowledge and unaware of benefits are the barriers for consumers to purchase eco friendly products. Hence, null hypothesis is accepted.
2. The high cost, lack of availability and non-durability values are more than the 0.05 value. Hence, there is a significant difference between in the above barriers and income group of the respondent. It implies that high cost, lack availability and non-durability are not the barriers for consumers to purchase green products. Hence, null hypothesis is rejected and alternative hypothesis is accepted.

Findings of the study:

1. Majority of the respondents are belonging to the age group of 31-40.
2. Nearly 63% of the respondents are having the educational qualification of graduation.
3. 50% of the respondents are having the monthly income ranges from Rs.25001-50000.
4. Product label and outdoor advertisement are major sources of awareness towards eco-friendly products.
5. Majority of the consumers are aware of the Eco-friendly FMCG products and are having a positive attitude towards green FMCG products.

6. It was found that the lack of knowledge and lack of awareness about the benefits are won't be barriers for purchasing eco-friendly products.
7. The study reveals that high cost, lack availability and non-durability are not the barriers for consumers to purchase green products.
8. Majority of the respondents prefer to buy eco-friendly products for health purpose.

CONCLUSION

The study concludes that consumer is opening up to the virtues of green products. But it is still a new concept for the majority. The new green movements need to reach out all and that will take a lot of time and efforts. The government has to join their hands together with green products manufacturing organisations to promote Eco-Friendly products, it will help in bringing the ecological balance and consumer plays vital role in success of this products. Hence, think once while buying products because your shopping decision can bring ecological balance and save the earth.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Akehurst, G., Afonso, C., & Gonçalves, H. M. (2012). Re-examining green purchase behaviour and the green consumer profile: new evidences. *Management Decision*, 50(5), 972-988.
- [2]. Akter, J. (2012). Consumer Attitude towards Green Marketing in Bangladesh. *ASA University Review*, 6(1), 158-166.
- [3]. Albayrak, T., Caber, M., Moutinho, L., & Herstein, R. (2011). The influence of skepticism on green purchase behavior. *International Journal of Business and Social Science*, 2(13), 189-197.
- [4]. Awad, T. A. (2011). Environmental segmentation alternatives: buyers' profiles and implications. *Journal of Islamic Marketing*, 2(1), 55-73.
- [5]. Bamberg, S. (2003). How does environmental concern influence specific environmentally related behaviors? A new answer to an old question. *Journal of environmental psychology*, 23(1), 21-32.
- [6]. Bearse, S., Capozucca, P., Favret, L., and Lynch, B. (2009). Finding the green in today's shoppers. *Sustainability trends and new shopper insights. GMA/Deloitte Green Shopper Study*.
- [7]. Borin, N., Lindsey-Mullikin, J., & Krishnan, R. (2013). An analysis of consumer reactions to green strategies. *Journal of Product & Brand Management*, 22(2), 118-128.
- [8]. Carrete, L., Castaño, R., Felix, R., Centeno, E., & González, E. (2012). Green consumer behavior in an emerging economy: confusion, credibility, and compatibility. *Journal of Consumer Marketing*, 29(7), 470-481.
- [9]. Chamorro, A., Rubio, S., & Miranda, F. J. (2009). Characteristics of research on green marketing. *Business Strategy and the Environment*, 18(4), 223-239.
- [10]. Chan, R. Y. (2001). Determinants of Chinese consumers' green purchase behavior. *Psychology & Marketing*, 18(4), 389-413.
- [11]. Cheah, I., & Phau, I. (2011). Attitudes towards environmentally friendly products: The influence of Eco literacy, interpersonal influence and value orientation. *Marketing Intelligence & Planning*, 29(5), 452-472.
- [12]. Chen, T. B., & Chai, L. T. (2010). Attitude towards the environment and green products: Consumers' perspective. *Management, Science and Engineering*, 4(2), 27-39.
- [13]. Chen, Y. S., & Chang, C. H. (2012). Enhance green purchase intentions: The roles of green perceived value, green perceived risk, and green trust. *Management Decision*, 50(3), 502-520.
- [14]. D'Souza, C., Taghian, M., Lamb, P., & Peretiatko, R. (2007). Green decisions: demographics and consumer understanding of environmental labels. *International Journal of Consumer Studies*, 31(4), 371-376.
- [15]. Dangelico, R. M., & Pujari, D. (2010). Mainstreaming green product innovation: Why and how companies integrate environmental sustainability. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 95(3), 471-486.
- [16]. Erdogan, M., Akbunar, S., Asik, U. O., Kaplan, H., & Kayir, C. G. (2012). The effects of demographic variables on students' responsible environmental behaviors. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 46, 3244-3248.
- [17]. Gilg, A., Barr, S., & Ford, N. (2005). Green consumption or sustainable lifestyles? Identifying the sustainable consumer. *Futures*, 37(6), 481-504.
- [18]. Gupta, S., & Ogdin, D. T. (2009). To buy or not to buy? A social dilemma perspective on green buying. *Journal of Consumer Marketing*, 26(6), 376-391.
- [19]. Hamid, S. A. R., Ghafoor, H. A., & Shah, T. Z. (2012). Analysis of attitude towards green purchase: Pakistan in context. *International journal of business and social science*, 3(6), 112-115.
- [20]. Irvani, D. M. R., Zadeh, S. M., Forozia, A., Shafaruddin, N., & Mahroein, H. (2012). Study of Factors Affecting Young Consumers to Choose Green Products. *Journal of Applied Science Research*, 2(6), 5534-

5544.

- [21]. Jain, S. K., & Kaur, G. (2004). Green marketing: An attitudinal and behavioural analysis of Indian consumers. *Global Business Review*, 5(2), 187-205.
- [22]. Khan, A., Khan, M.N., and Siddiqui, T.Z. (2013). Gauging attitudes towards the environment through NEP: a case study from India. *International Journal of Social Entrepreneurship and Innovation*, 2(1), 42-51.
- [23]. Khare, A. (2014). Consumers' susceptibility to interpersonal influence as a determining factor of ecologically conscious behaviour. *Marketing Intelligence & Planning*, 32(1), 2-20.
- [24]. Lee, K. (2009). Gender differences in Hong Kong adolescent consumers' green purchasing behavior. *Journal of consumer marketing*, 26(2), 87-96.
- [25]. Mourad, M., & Ahmed, Y. S. E. (2012). Perception of green brand in an emerging innovative market. *European Journal of Innovation Management*, 15(4), 514-537.
- [26]. Nath, V., Kumar, R., Agrawal, R., Gautam, A., & Sharma, V. (2013). Consumer Adoption of Green Products: Modeling the Enablers. *Global Business Review*, 14(3), 453-470.
- [27]. Olson, E. L. (2013). It's not easy being green: the effects of attribute tradeoffs on green product preference and choice. *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, 41(2), 171-184.
- [28]. Peattie, K. (1999). Trappings versus substance in the greening of marketing planning. *Journal of Strategic Marketing*, 7(2), 131
- [29]. International
- [30]. Peattie, K. (2001). Towards sustainability: the third age of green marketing. *The Marketing Review*, 2(2), 129-146.
- [31]. Peattie, K., & Charter, M. (2003). Green marketing. *The marketing book*, 5, 726-75
- [32]. Polonsky, M. J. (1994). An introduction to green marketing. *Electronic Green Journal*, 1(2).
- [33]. Polonsky, M. J. (2011). Transformative Green Marketing: Impediments and Opportunities. *Journal of Business Research*, 64(12), 1311-1319.
- [34]. Rice, G. (2006). Pro-environmental behavior in Egypt: Is there a role for Islamic environmental ethics?. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 65(4), 373-390.
- [35]. Smith, K. T., & Brower, T. R. (2012). Longitudinal study of green marketing strategies that influence Millennials. *Journal of Strategic Marketing*, 20(6), 535-551.
- [36]. Stone, G., Montgomery, C., & Nkonge, J. (2008). Do Consumer's Environmental Attitudes Translate into Actions: A Five Nation Cross-Cultural Analysis. *Advances in Marketing: Issues, Strategies and Theories*, 197.
- [37]. Tang, E.P., and Chan, R.Y. (1998). Purchasing behaviours and perceptions of environmentally harmful products. *Marketing Intelligence & Planning*, 16(6), 356-362.
- [38]. Tang, Y., Wang, X., & Lu, P. (2014). Chinese consumer attitude and purchase intent towards green products. *Asia-Pacific Journal of Business Administration*, 6(2), 84-96.
- [39]. Verma, H. V. (2002). Green consumer: an initial study. *Management and Labour Studies*, 27(2), 77-88.
- [40]. Wasik, J.F. (1996). *Green marketing and management: A global perspective*. Cambridge, Mass: Blackwell Publishers Inc.